

Automatic Weather Stations

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Automatic Weather Stations

CONTENTS

	Page
Introduction	2
Planning an Automatic Weather Station	3
Barometric Pressure and Rainfall	4
Wind Speed and Direction	5
Solar Irradiance	6
Temperature and Humidity	7
Soil Moisture Measurement	8
Data Storage	9
Data Transmission	10
Power Supplies	11
Enclosures and Towers	12

Automatic Weather Stations

Collection and analysis of weather information from individual or networked locations can be carried out automatically where sites are too remote, or inconvenient for regular attendance to collect data manually.

The Munro Automatic Weather Station is a customised installation for unattended recording, processing and transmission of data to a control centre. There is a wide range of options in terms of weather and other parameters that may be recorded; data storage and retrieval methods and systems networking.

Munro provides a comprehensive advisory service for the design of stations for all environments and systems are available built to meet British Meteorological Office requirements.

Note : A separate catalogue describes the range of Munro equipment for manually-operated stations.

A Typical Automatic Station

A typical automatic weather station, as supplied by Munro, would comprise the site equipment shown on the illustration, together with all necessary accessories. Remote stations may require further communications and data storage facilities. Other sensors and accessories can also be incorporated according to local requirements. The catalogue pages provide more information on equipment available. In all cases, Munro will advise customers on selection prior to final order.

Planning an Automatic Weather Station

In planning a new AWS, the selection of equipment depends on the nature of the regular data required and the site location. Consideration should also be given to whether the versatility of the system might be enhanced by the economic addition of further sensors. The range of sensors and other equipment available is wide and selection of proven components in consultation with an experienced company like Munro is a guarantee of trouble-free performance for the future.

Sensors are available to suit every requirement, including wind speed and direction, temperature and humidity, rainfall, solar radiation, water and snow depth, soil moisture measurement and other factors. The information obtained is recorded in a data logger for transmission by telephone line, radio or satellite link to a control centre, with PC and peripheral equipment as required. Systems should be simple to program and easy to operate, with no special experience. Several stations can be networked, if required, to cover a wide area.

Most sensors and accessory equipment would normally be mounted on a suitable tower installed on site. Power supplies are usually self-contained and provided by batteries automatically recharged from a solar panel. Weatherproof enclosures on the tower will protect equipment, such as the data logger, storage modules, modems and some sensors.

Munro technical staff are ready to give unbiased and comprehensive advice on the design and installation of your station, to ensure that operational efficiency is matched to the requirements of the project.

A Typical Automatic Weather Station would consist of:-

Sensors: PTB101 Barometric Pressure Sensor
R100 Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge
A100 Wind Speed Sensor
W200 Wind Direction Sensor
CM3 Pyranometer
HMP45C Temperature & Humidity Sensor

Data Storage: CR10X Data Logger
CSM1 Card Storage Module
SMC 1024 Memory Cards

Data Retrieval: MCR1 Memory Card Reader

Power: SOP10/X Solar Panel
PS12E-ALK 12V Alkaline Power Supply

Hardware: UT930 Instrument Tower
ENC 12/14 Enclosure
URS1 Unaspirated Radiation Shield
016E Pyranometer Mounting Arm
017E Combined Wind Sensor Cross-arm

Additional sensors available for : Soil Temperature, Soil Moisture, Soil Heat Flux, Water and Snow Depth and Visibility. Please contact R W Munro for full details and prices.

Communication packages are available to transfer the Data by Telephone Modem, Radio Modem and Satellite Link. R W Munro will be pleased to offer advice, details and prices.

Barometric Pressure and Rainfall

Barometric Pressure Sensor PTB101B

The sensor has a range of 600-1060hPa and is fabricated from two pieces of silicon, with one piece acting as a pressure sensitive diaphragm and the other as a rigid support plate. Pressure variations deflect the diaphragm and change the sensor's capacitance which is converted to an analogue voltage output as a measure of ambient pressure. The PTB101B can be operated in continuous or shutdown mode, the latter mode turned on and off by a control signal which minimises power consumption, although a warm-up period of one second must be allowed. The PTB101B is housed in a plated copper case, fitted with an intake valve for pressure equilibrium.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	PTB101B
Operating range	600 mb to 1060 mb (hPa)
Temperature range	-40°C to +60°C
Humidity range	Non-condensing
Linearity	±0.45 mb
Hysteresis	±0.03 mb
Repeatability	±0.03 mb
Drift	< ±0.1 mb per year
Current consumption	< 4 mA on & 1 µA off
Output voltage	2 to 2.5 V dc
Warm-up time	1 second
Size	59 x 97 x 21 mm
Weight	130 g

Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge R100 Series

Ideal for remote monitoring, the bucket is divided into two parts and mounted on a tungsten axle and pivots. When one part fills, the bucket tips to discharge the water to the ground and also activates a pair of switches. The other part of the bucket then fills, and the cycle is repeated as long as rain is falling. Other features include a wire mesh filter to keep out debris and insects, a levelling adjustment with indicator and the option of heating to prevent ice forming in the bucket assembly down to a temperature of -6°C. A cover with a deep funnel inlet can also be provided to prevent rain bouncing out during downpours.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	R102	R104	R106
Diameter of aperture	203 mm	203 mm	203 mm
Area of aperture	32365 mm ²	32365 mm ²	32365 mm ²
Rainfall capacity	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited
Calibration	0.2 mm per tip	0.5 mm per tip	0.25 mm per tip
Dimensions			
Base dia.	280 mm	280 mm	280 mm
Height (std. cover)	310 mm	310 mm	310 mm
Height (deep cover)	437 mm	437 mm	437 mm
Weight (std. cover)	5.8 kg	5.8 kg	5.8 kg
Weight (deep cover)	7 kg	7 kg	7 kg
Base fixing	3 x 9.9 mm holes on 260 mm PCD	3 x 9.9 mm holes on 260 mm PCD	3 x 9.9 mm holes on 260 mm PCD
Heating	12 V dc 1.45 A	12 V dc 1.45 A	12 V dc 1.45 A

Wind Speed and Direction

Switching Anemometer A100R

Accurate measurements of wind run or mean wind speed are provided by this precision sensor. A magnet turns with the rotor spindle to produce a varying field, which causes a mercury-wetted reed switch to make and break contact once per revolution of the rotor. No power is required apart from that required to detect contact closure, so the A100R is well suited for use on remote sites. Construction is of anodised aluminium alloy, stainless steel and weather-resisting plastics and uses corrosion resistant protected ball-bearings. The instrument is designed for permanent exposure to the weather.

Potentiometer Wind Vane W200P

A sensitive instrument ideal for remote operation, the W200P Wind Vane incorporates a micro-torque wire-wound potentiometer, with the small 2° gap at North filled to ensure smooth operation. Precision ball-bearing races are corrosion-resistant and protected against the entry of moisture and dust. The fin is attached by a patented gravity-sensitive fastener which allows rapid fixing and release when the Wind Vane is used as a portable instrument.

SPECIFICATIONS

A100R		W200P	
Stalling speed	0.2 m/s	Threshold	0.6 m/s
Max. speed	>75 m/s	Max. speed	>75 m/s
Accuracy	±0.1 m/s	Response	Distance constant 2.3 m
Distance constant	2.3 m		Damping ratio 0.2
Calibration	0.80 rev. per metre (1 pulse per 1.25 metres)	Range	360° mechanical angle 360° continuous rotation allowed
Switch life	Rated 25x10 ⁹ operations min.	Accuracy	±2°
Size	Height 200 mm Case dia. 55 mm Standard rotor 150 mm dia.	Resolution	±0.2°
Temperature range	-30°C to +70°C	Repeatability	±0.5°
Switching Voltage	100 V dc max.	Life	5x10 ⁷ rev. (10 years typical exposure)
Switching Current	40 mA max.	Size	Overall height 270 mm Case dia. 56 mm Fin clearance 180 mm
Switching Rating	4 W max.	Weight	350 g (inc. standard cable)
Actuating time	1.5 ms	Potentiometer	Resistance 1k ohm ±10%
Switch bounce	nil		

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Solar Irradiance

Thermopile Pyranometer CM3

Complying with ISO 9060, the CM3 Pyranometer provides accurate measurement of direct and diffuse solar irradiance. The irradiant energy absorbed by the disc is converted into a voltage. The sensor is a high quality blackened thermopile, producing a flat spectral response over the full solar spectrum. A glass dome shields the unit and allows equal transmission of the direct solar component for every position of the sun.

Thermopile Pyranometer CM6B

Similar in operation to the CM3, this sensor meets the WMO 'first-class' specification. It has a 64-thermocouple thermopile, which is rotationally symmetrical and housed under K5 glass domes. A white screen stops the body of the pyranometer heating up and a drying cartridge stops condensation on the inside of the sensor. A spirit level and levelling screws are provided.

SPECIFICATIONS

CM3

Spectral range	305 - 2800 nm (50% points)
Sensitivity	10 - 35 $\mu\text{V}/\text{Wm}^2$
Spectral selectivity	$\pm 5\%$ (350-1500nm)
Response time	95% 18 s
Non-stability	<1% change per year
Non-linearity	$\pm 2.5\%$ (<1000Wm ²)
Tilt response	< $\pm 2\%$
Operating temperature	-40 to +80°C

CM6B

Spectral range	305-2800 nm (50% points) 335-2200 nm (95% points)
Sensitivity	9-15 $\mu\text{V}/\text{Wm}^2$
Spectral selectivity	$\pm 2\%$
Response time	63% 5 s, 99% 55 s
Directional error	< $\pm 20 \text{ Wm}^2$ @ 1000 Wm ²
Non-linearity	$\pm 1.5\%$ @ <1000 Wm ²
Tilt error	<1.5% @ 1000 Wm ²
Operating temperature	-40 to +90°C

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Temperature and Humidity

Temperature and Relative Humidity Probe HMP45C

Incorporating a capacitive relative humidity sensor and precision thermistor, the HMP45C features good long term stability and low power consumption, and is ideal for industrial and scientific applications. Designed for use in a wide range of environments, the IP65 protected probe is insensitive to dust and has a high tolerance to chemicals. Normally installed in a radiation shield, the HMP45C has high accuracy and negligible hysteresis. The probe head, containing the sensor and electronics, is quickly and easily removed from the probe body to enable field calibration without interrupting measurements for long periods.

SPECIFICATIONS

HMP45C	
Relative Humidity Range	0.8 to 100% RH
Output scale	0 to 100% RH = 0 to 1 V dc
Against factory reference	±1% RH
Against field reference	±2% RH (0 to 90% RH) ±3% RH (90 to 100% RH)
Long term stability	Better than 1% RH per year
Temperature range	-39.2 to +60°C
Accuracy	±0.5°C at -39°C ±0.2°C at +20°C ±0.4°C at +60°C
Supply voltage	12v dc (7 to 35 V dc possible)
Power consumption	<4 mA
Output load	>10k ohm (to ground)

Temperature Probe T107 and T108

Designed for use in air, soil or water, the T107 Probe operates over a range of -40°C to +56°C, whereas the T108 Probe is for use from -3°C to +90°C. A precision thermistor built for long term stability, is incorporated in a water-resistant casing, which is provided with a standard 3m cable. Longer cable lengths up to 300m are available to special order. The only maintenance required is regular inspection of the tough UV-resistant polyurethane and totally waterproof cable. A radiation shield is available to minimise errors when measuring air temperatures in areas of high solar radiation.

Thermocouple Probe T105

Suitable for measuring air and soil temperatures, this thermocouple based probe is robustly constructed. The sensing junction is completely sealed and contained in a stainless steel sheath providing excellent protection when the probe is buried. The outer insulation is impervious to water with good mechanical properties and the cable is fully screened to minimise noise pick-up on long runs.

SPECIFICATIONS

	T107	T108	T105
Temperature range	-40 to + 56°C	-3 to + 90°C	-70 to + 100°C
Accuracy (worst case)	±0.4°C	±0.1°C	±0.5°C
Accuracy (typical)	±0.2°C	±0.07°C	±0.5°C
Sensing device	Precision Thermistor	Precision Thermistor	Thermocouple, Copper-constantan
Cable length	3 m (standard)	3 m (standard)	3 m (standard)
Cable strain relief (moulded)	30 x 10 mm dia.	30 x 10 mm dia.	30 x 10 mm dia.
Sensing head	60 x 5 mm dia.	60 x 5 mm dia.	60 x 5 mm dia.

Soil Moisture Measurements

Heat Flux Plate HFP01

Designed to measure heat flows, the most common application for this thermopile based sensor, is the measurement of heat flux in soils for meteorological energy balance measurements. Encapsulated in high thermal conductivity epoxy to prevent ground potential pick-up, the HFP01 has a high degree of stability and has an output voltage directly proportional to the local heat flux.

Soil Moisture Block 227

Soil water potential can be conveniently and economically estimated using gypsum soil moisture blocks. In the 227 Block, the gypsum is cast around two concentric electrodes which confine current flow to the interior of the Block. The 227 is configured for direct connection to the data logger. The gypsum block typically lasts one or two years, but block life can be maximised by removing from the field if not used during the winter.

Soil Moisture Sensor 257

Suitable for permanent location in the soil, this robust sensor consists of two concentric electrodes buried in a reference matrix material, which is protected from deterioration by a surrounding synthetic membrane. Calculation of the soil water potential can be done on line by the data logger in conjunction with a soil temperature measurement provided by the Temperature Probe 107.

SPECIFICATIONS

	HFP01	SMB227	SMS257
Measurement range	-30 to + 70°C	0.1 to 10 bar	0 to 2 bar
Conductivity range	0.1 to 1.7 W/m ²		
Sensitivity	50 μV/Wm ²		
Stability	<1% change per year		
Expected accuracy	±20% daily totals		
Cable length	5 m (standard)	7.5 m (standard)	7.5 m (standard)
Sensing head dimensions	5 x 80 mm dia.	28 x 22 mm dia.	80 x 22 mm dia.

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Data Storage

Data Logger CR10X

At the heart of a Munro Automatic Weather Station, this high accuracy measurement and control module data logger offers comprehensive data collection, storage and conversion facilities. It features 128k flash EEPROM, 128k of battery-backed RAM to store 62,000 data values, low battery voltage detection and it is protected against lightning damage. It can be reprogrammed in the field without a PC and has digital and analogue outputs for extra versatility. Sensors are powered directly from the data logger and need no external signal conditioning.

Data Storage Modules SM 192 and SM 716

When connected to the data logger, these compact storage modules collect and store all data being received. Alternatively, data can be copied to a module from one or more data loggers on site visits. Modules can also be used for program transfer to data loggers. SM 192 stores 96,000 data points, whilst SM 716 stores up to 358,000 data points. The modules are rugged, sealed devices, in a stainless steel packaging. PC208W Software is required.

Card Storage Module CSM1

The Card Storage Module system consists of a microprocessor-controlled read/write module and removable credit card sized memory cards that hold data in the battery backed memory. The memory cards are easily exchanged and transported to a computer for data retrieval. The Module is normally mounted within the Enclosure (ENC10/12 or ENC 12/14) and features built-in status indicators for module operation and storage. The Module has a low quiescent power consumption and a wide operating temperature range allowing it to be used in remote battery-powered applications.

Memory Card Reader MCR1

Designed to read and configure memory cards used with the Card Storage Module, the Memory Card Reader would normally be positioned in a data processing office or headquarters complex, where it is used to read cards sent in from one or more stations in a network. In function, the MCR1 is identical to the Card Storage Module, but offers a more compact and cost effective solution for card reading only.

Memory Cards for CSM1

Three types are available as follows: SMC1024 for 1024k byte, SMC2048 for 2048kbyte and SMC4096 for 4096k byte. Two cards per station are recommended.

Data Transmission

Telephone Modem COM200

Normally mounted within the enclosure, (ENC10/12 or ENC 12/14) the COM200 Modem enables communication between a computer and the data-logger over a public switched telephone network. A compatible modem is required at the computer; the COM200 is connected to the data-logger. Featuring a wide operating temperature range and low power requirements, the COM200 Modem is ideally suited for use in remote applications.

Asynchronous Short Range Modem RAD-SRM

Operating without any external power supply, the small amount of current required being drawn from the RS232 circuits, the RAD-SRM is ideal for communication with the data-logger at distances up to 18km. The Modem design ensures integrity of transmission using unconditioned 4-wire cable (two twisted pairs), at data rates up to 9600 baud.

Data Collection Via Satellite DCP1

The DCP1 series of Data Collection Platforms is based on a DCP Transmitter Unit which, with a simple antenna and power source, provides a system for collection of data from remote monitoring stations. In order to cover a wide range of applications, variations on the standard system are provided; for example, the standard Yaggi Antenna may be replaced by an omni-directional type for use on moving platforms or ships.

The DCP Transmitter contains an accurate clock for transmission timing purposes. However, over long periods of time the clock will have to be checked/reset using a Synchroniser unit. For installations in remote areas, where access to the DCP may be difficult, we recommend that the Model 2099 Synchroniser is permanently fitted. This will acquire GPS timing signals and automatically check and update the DCP clock when necessary. With the 2099 Synchroniser connected the DCP Transmitter can also be configured to include Latitude and Longitude position information in the transmission messages.

Using a DCP System, the user can collect data from any remote environmental monitoring station, quickly and reliably via one of the World Meteorological Organisation Geostationary Satellites (METEOSAT, GOES etc)

This system offers a data collection facility which is price competitive with other telemetry systems, but also offers fast, easy installation, as well as reliable transmission of data, even in severe weather conditions.

Power Supplies

Power Supplies PS12E

The PS12E Power Supply for the data logger is available in two forms, with alkaline batteries (PS12E-ALK) or lead-acid batteries (PS12E-LA). The PS12E-ALK has eight alkaline D-cells providing 12.4V, with a nominal rating of 7.5Ah capacity at 20°C. It can be used with a lead-acid battery connected in parallel to the data logger, the alkaline battery acting as back-up. The PS12E-LA is a 12V, 7.0Ah lead-acid battery, with a temperature compensated charging circuit.

Solarex Solar Panels SOP5/X and SOP10/X

These 5W and 10W solar panels, are normally used with data loggers operating with relatively few sensors and where power requirements are small. The panels generate enough power to maintain a float charge on a lead-acid battery, allowing the data logger to be powered continuously. Versions with a shunt regulator, (SOP5 and SOP10) are available, supplied only to special order.

Solarex Solar Panel SOP18

This panel may be supplied, if the data logger is to be used with peripherals consuming a significant amount of power.

RTDM Software

Real-Time Software

Real Time Data Monitor (RTDM) is a powerful program that allows you to design display screens on which you can view real-time, pseudo real-time or archived data logger data. The RTDM designer environment gives you complete control over how your data is displayed and allows the creation of attractive, professional displays by means of colour, images and drawing tools.

RTDM includes comprehensive, context-sensitive on-line help and a demonstration display to illustrate some of the capabilities of the program.

RTDM reads data from a Munro data file on the PC's hard disk. The data file may have been retrieved from a data logger (e.g. using the PC208W Data logger Support Software) or generated from an original data file by Munro's Split program. RTDM can read data files generated by more than one data logger, allowing the designer to display data from multiple stations on one screen.

RTDM checks the data file for new data at a user-specified interval. A near-real-time display can be achieved by retrieving data frequently and checking the data file frequently. However, in many applications, an update every few minutes (or less) is sufficient and will reduce the time for which the PC must be on-line to the data logger. The maximum speed of operation will depend on the communication link to the data logger and the specification of the PC.

Enclosures and Towers

Enclosures ENC 10/12 and ENC12/14

Munro enclosures for the site protection of data loggers, power supplies and peripherals, are constructed from white, fibreglass-reinforced polyester with a punched anodised aluminium chassis plate for easy attachment of equipment. Doors can be padlocked. No radiation or rain shield is required. A venting plug allows pressure equalisation between the inside and outside of the enclosure. When an enclosure is bought as a configured system, all components will be pre-fitted. The ENC 10/12 has space for only one small peripheral in addition to power supplies and data logger. The ENC 12/14 will accept most sizes of peripheral. The enclosures may be wall or pole mounted.

Instrumentation Tower UT930

This guyed, 10m tubular aluminium tower, is in three sections with a 0.5m mast. The base and anchors for guy ropes must be concreted into the ground. The triangular, braced cross sections provide strength with light weight and the tower can be erected easily by one person.

Instrumentation Towers ATW2 and ATW3

These rugged 2m and 3m towers for permanent weather stations are concreted into the ground and require no guy ropes.

Portable Tripods CM10/2 and CM10/3

Requiring no guy ropes or concreting, these steel tripods can be moved from site to site as required and can be set up on uneven ground. In 2m and 3m sizes.

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